

DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES BASED ON THE TRANSFORMATION OF WORLD HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Аннотация. Ушбу илмий мақолада жаҳоннинг нуфузли олий таълим муассасаларини халқаро стандартлар асосида трансформация қилиш асосида ривожлантириш стратегиялари тажрибалари таҳлилий ўрганилган.

Калит сўзлар: рақамлаштириш, трансформация, халқаро стандартлар, стратегия.

Аннотация. В данной научной статье анализируется опыт престижных высших учебных заведений мира по разработке стратегий, основанных на трансформации на основе международных стандартов.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, трансформация, международные стандарты, стратегия.

Abstract. In this scientific article, the experiences of development strategies based on the transformation of prestigious higher education institutions of the world based on international standards are analytically studied.

Key words: digitization, transformation, international standards, strategy.

The current stage of global development is characterized by active entry into the era of the fourth industrial revolution, which leads to dynamic, large-scale and multifaceted changes in the field of higher education. Representing one of the fairly stable system-forming social institutions of society, global higher education is forced to promptly and adequately respond to new challenges and promptly acquire new forms.

The sphere of higher education is currently undergoing fundamental changes in terms of its role in the economy and society, principles and methods of work, organization and management. The world's leading universities are searching for new models, actively rethinking their missions, trying to go beyond traditional functions and institutional forms, developing and implementing new technologies. Due to the fact that these changes concern the entire range of basic functions of modern universities in various countries, we can talk about a global transformation of university models.

Despite the multiplicity of interpretations of university models, one of the most recognized is the approach that determines the trajectory of change of modern universities in the direction of the University 3.0 model. This approach is based on the concept of J. Wissem [1], according to which University 3.0 is transformed from the previous models 1.0 and 2.0, simultaneously implementing three missions: educational, research and innovation, aimed at the commercialization of knowledge. This concept was used as the basis for the research methodology. As a hypothesis, it was suggested that, in addition to the active transition of many universities to the University 3.0 model, in modern conditions a new promising and future-oriented University 4.0 model is being formed. Its mission is defined not only as education,

science and innovation, but also as the integration of various structures of society to solve the problems of sustainable development of society.

The study attempted to analyze the real target models of various universities around the world and, on this basis, to form a set of characteristics of typological models of universities on a scale of 1.0–4.0 and to identify the main trends in the transformation of higher education in the projection of the university of the future. Since the target model of a university is embedded in its development strategy, strategic documents of various universities around the world were used for the analysis. In particular, programs, strategies, concepts, visions, and strategic plans for their development, posted on the official websites of universities, were analyzed.

The study was conducted using the method of qualitative analysis of documents. The formulations of the mission, strategic goals, and main areas of activity of universities were directly analyzed. They were defined as the main categories of analysis, since they reflect the target development models to the greatest extent. Using a comparative analysis of these formulations, typological models of universities were constructed on a scale of 1.0–4.0 based on the definition of their main characteristics. This made it possible to concretize the appearance of these models and outline the directions of transformation of universities around the world in terms of the most promising models.

The selection of universities for the analysis of their strategic documents was carried out based on the results of the global QS World University Rankings 2022, the published part of which included 1,300 universities. For analysis, strategic documents of foreign universities located in three regions (Europe, Asia, North America), occupying different positions in the ranking, as well as leading Russian universities, whose strategic documents are posted in the public domain, were selected. In total, strategic documents of 30 universities were analyzed, including 20 foreign and 10 Russian.

An analysis of strategic documents for the development of world universities has shown that their target models are largely determined by the development guidelines of national higher education systems. Depending on the content of the strategic goals formulated in the documents, all analyzed universities were conditionally divided into two large groups:

1) universities aimed at increasing their influence at the global level - these are mainly leading European, American and almost all Asian universities, as well as some leading Russian universities;

2) universities aimed at leading positions at the national and regional levels - these are mainly British, some North American universities, as well as most Russian universities.

The results of the study indicate that the processes of transformation of modern university models are actively underway. Despite the fact that chronologically, university models from 1.0 to 4.0 were formed consistently in history, today there are universities in the world that correspond to all these models. Moreover, in reality, mixed and transitional models are more common. The presented set of basic characteristics of typological university models can serve as a tool for assessing the compliance of a specific university with a particular model on a scale of 1.0–4.0, as well as for building long-term trajectories of its development. Since many universities in the world, including Russian ones, face the super-ambitious tasks of entering the world elite of higher education, it is already necessary to focus on the models of the university of the future. This implies a significant increase in the innovative and integration potential of the university with the help of modern digital solutions, the growth of its social responsibility, the formation of the university as a large ecosystem, a multifunctional platform for cooperation, a global communication center focused on the reproduction of a new type of society. The defining

parameters in the formation of the university of the future are a focus on innovation, advanced continuous education, managed broad integration, diversification of income sources, social involvement and contribution to sustainable development.

An analysis of various typological and target models of universities has shown that the university is becoming an increasingly important element of society. At the same time, each country from the entire variety of development paths must choose the strategy for universities that best suits its potential and resources [2], which means that national higher education systems and each university will be characterized by their own unique trajectories. In practice, the transition to a new model is an extremely complex task that requires a comprehensive restructuring of existing educational organizations and the system of their interactions. Questions remain open about possible scenarios for the development of universities within the framework of various national systems, about accelerated paths of transition from one model to another, about the possibilities of trans-model transitions. Nevertheless, even now, knowing the characteristics of the university of the future, it is necessary to think and act proactively, since competent implementation of strategic planning and forecasting allows you to manage the future.

REFERENCES

1. Wissema J.G. Third Generation University: University Management in the Transition Period. Moscow: Sberbank, 2016. 422 p. ISBN: 978-5-9693-0299-0
2. Salmi D. Creating World-Class Universities: Trans. from English. Moscow: Ves' Mir, 2009. 132 p. ISBN: 978-5-7777-0448-1